

HIV SENTINEL SURVEILLANCE (ANC)

Andhra Pradesh State Report

2018-19

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MEDICAL RESEARCH | NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF
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Foreword

HIV Sentinel surveillance among ANC attendees is one of the most important national level activities, as it helps the programme managers in framing health policies towards controlling HIV infection in the state and the country as well. The objectives of HIV sentinel surveillance are to understand the trends, assess spread and distribution of HIV infection among geographical areas across the state. In order to have uniform geographical coverage, the number of sentinel sites in the state has been increased over a period of years by keeping at least one site in each district.

The National Institute of Epidemiology, Chennai, one of the Regional Institutes for 8 southern states, is involved in the HIV surveillance activities since 2006. This report is prepared based on the data collected during the 16th round of surveillance, in conjunction with the past years data to analyze the trend and to have an insight of epidemiological factors. I hope this report will serve as a very useful tool for the policy makers, scholars, researchers and other stakeholders in formulating guidelines in controlling HIV and enhancing their knowledge of HIV in their state.

I take this opportunity to thank Dr. Shobini Rajan, Assistant Director General, NACO and Dr. Pradeep Kumar, Consultant (surveillance) & his team for entrusting this activity to NIE and also for providing technical support in implementing the surveillance. I also wish to thank the Project Director and nodal officer of State AIDS Control Society for their help in completing the surveillance activities in a timely manner. I express my gratitude to all the State Referral Laboratories, National Referral Laboratories, State Surveillance Team members, Sentinel sites personnel and other National and International partners who helped us in completing the surveillance successfully.

Dr. Manoj V Murhekar

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Suggested citation

ICMR - National Institute of Epidemiology (2020). HIV Sentinel Surveillance 2018-19, Andhra Pradesh State Report: Indian Council of Medical Research, Department of Health Research, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India.

ISSN 2583-2336

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Contents

Chapter 1: Introduction	9
1.1. HIV Sentinel Surveillance	10
Chapter 2: Methodology and Implementation	12
2.1. Implementation Structure of HIV Sentinel Surveillance in India	12
2.2. Initiatives during HSS 2018-19:	13
2.3. Methodology of HSS at ANC Sentinel Sites:	16
2.4. Information Collected under HSS at ANC Sentinel Sites	18
Chapter 3. Profile of Respondents	20
Chapter 4. Distribution and HIV Prevalence by Socio-demographic variables	23
Chapter 4.1 Distribution and HIV Prevalence by Age Group.	23
Chapter 4.2 Distribution and HIV Prevalence by Literacy Status	23
Chapter 4.3 Distribution and HIV Prevalence by Order of Pregnancy	24
Chapter 4.4 Distribution and HIV Prevalence by Duration of Pregnancy	24
Chapter 4.5 Distribution and HIV Prevalence by ANC Service Utilization	25
Chapter 4.6 Distribution and HIV Prevalence by Source of Referral	25
Chapter 4.7 Distribution and HIV Prevalence by Place of Residence	26
Chapter 4.8 Distribution and HIV Prevalence by Occupation of the Respondent	26
Chapter 4.9 Distribution and HIV Prevalence by Occupation of the Respondents' Spouse	27
Chapter 4.10 Distribution and HIV Prevalence by Migration Status of the Respondents' Spouse.	28
Chapter 4.11 Distribution and HIV Prevalence by HIV Test History	29
Chapter 4.12 Distribution and HIV Prevalence by HIV Management	29
Chapter 5.	30
Chapter 5.1 District-wise Distribution of Respondents, HIV Prevalence and Trend	30
Chapter 5.2. HIV Prevalence trend at district level	49
Chapter 6 Summary	54

CHAPTER 1.

INTRODUCTION: HIV AND HSS

Acquired immune deficiency syndrome or acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS), caused by the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), progressively reduces the effectiveness of the immune system, leaving the infected susceptible to opportunistic infections. HIV was first reported in USA in 1981, following which the infection spread globally. Three decades since its inception, the epidemic still continues to be a global public health threat and interventions at various levels are ongoing for HIV management. Unprotected sex, sharing used needles or syringes and transfusion of untested blood increases the risks of HIV infection.

The first HIV case in India was reported in 1986 in Chennai, followed by a rapid spread across the nation within a decade. Based on their risk of disease transmission and HIV prevalence levels, the population in India is divided into 3 categories high-risk groups with - high prevalence, bridge populations with moderate prevalence and general population low prevalence.

Figure 1: HIV Transmission Dynamics among HIV Sub-population groups

HIV in India is highly concentrated among the high-risk population groups. Unprotected sex with female sex workers (FSW), injecting drug users (IDU), and unprotected anal sex between men are the three primary routes of HIV transmission in India. The bridge population, generally the clients or partners of high-risk population, transmit the disease to the general population. Hence measures to reduce the HIV prevalence levels in high-risk population has been observed as an effective method to reduce the transmission risks.

1.1 HIV Sentinel Surveillance (HSS)

HIV sentinel surveillance is defined as a system of monitoring the HIV epidemic among the specified population groups by collecting information on HIV from designated sites (sentinel sites) over years, through a uniform and consistent methodology that allows comparison of findings across place and time, to guide programme response. A sentinel site is a designated service point/facility where blood specimens and relevant information are collected from a fixed number of eligible individuals from a specified population group over a fixed period of time, periodically, for the purpose of monitoring the HIV epidemic.

Figure 2: Evolution of HIV sentinel surveillance in India

The HIV sentinel surveillance (HSS) in India was initiated in 1985 among the blood donors and patients with STIs by the Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR). It is one of the largest HSS systems in the world which helps to understand the dynamics of the HIV epidemic and monitor the trends among different population groups and geographical areas. It provides inputs to the programme for strengthening prevention and control activities. The sentinel sites have been scaled up in a phased manner from 176 in 1998 (including 92 ANC sites) to 1359 in 2010-11 (including 696 ANC sites). HSS 2019 was implemented at 776 ANC sites. In continuation, the 16th round of HIV Sentinel Surveillance (HSS) among antenatal care (ANC) clinic attendees was implemented during year 2019 at 833 sites across 35 States/UTs and 642 districts (out of total of 727 districts). This is highest in various rounds of HSS under NACP till now.

Figure 3: Objectives and Application of HIV Sentinel Surveillance

CHAPTER 2

HSS - METHODOLOGY AND IMPLEMENTATION

2.1 Implementation Structure of HIV Sentinel Surveillance in India

HIV sentinel surveillance has a robust structure for planning, implementation, and review. It follows a four-tier supervisory structure at national, regional, state, and district levels.

National level Organizations and Institutes act as Nodal Agencies while the 8 regional institutes provide technical support to the State AIDS Control Societies (SACS) for all HSS activities. SACS is primarily responsible for implementation of HSS in their respective states with the support of functional district AIDS Prevention and Control Units (DAPCUs), for coordination of HSS activities at the sentinel sites and the associated testing labs. The entire HSS structure is involved the assessment of HSS implementation plans and review of the outcomes of each round.

Figure 4: Implementation Structure of HSS

Table 1: Regional Institutes and their States Covered

Name of regional institution	Responsible states
Central: All India Institute of Medical Science, New Delhi	Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Jharkhand, Uttaranchal, and Delhi.
North: Postgraduate Institute of Medical Education and Research, Chandigarh	Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Punjab, and Chandigarh.
West: National AIDS Research Institute, Pune	Maharashtra, Gujarat, Goa, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, Daman & Diu, and Dadra Nagar Haveli.
South: National Institute of Epidemiology, Chennai	Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Kerala, Odisha, Puducherry, and Lakshadweep and Telangana.
East: National Institute of Cholera and Enteric Diseases, Kolkata	West Bengal, Chhattisgarh, Sikkim, Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Meghalaya, and Nagaland.
Northeast: Regional Institute of Medical Sciences, Imphal	Manipur, Mizoram, Tripura, Assam, and Arunachal Pradesh.

2.2 Initiatives during HSS 2018-19:

In response to key issues identified in the implementation of HSS during the previous rounds as well as to improve the quality and promptness of the surveillance, several new initiatives were implemented in the 16th round, as part of continuous quality improvement.

SACS checklist for preparatory activities:

- Developed to monitor the planning process for HSS in each state (Annex 3).
- All preparatory activities were broken into specific tasks with clear timelines and all SACS were required to submit the completion status for each task.
- A team of officers from NACO coordinated with state nodal persons to ensure that preparatory activities in all states adhered to the timelines.

Pre-surveillance sentinel site evaluation (SSE):

- A pre-surveillance evaluation of ANC and STD sentinel sites was conducted to identify and correct human resources and infrastructure-related issues at the sentinel sites before initiation of surveillance.
- The evaluation also provided site information such as type of facility, average OPD attendance, availability of HIV and AIDS services, and distance of facilities from HSS labs (Annex 4), which may have implications on adherence to methodology.

Standard operational manuals, wall charts, and bilingual data forms:

- Developed to simplify the HSS methodology for site-level personnel and to ensure uniform implementation of the guidelines in all the sentinel sites.
- These were printed centrally and distributed across the country.

Training during HSS 2018-19:

Steps to improve quality of training:

1. A well-structured training programme was adopted to ensure that all the personnel involved in HSS at different levels were adequately and uniformly trained in the respective areas of responsibility.
2. The training agenda, curriculum, and planning and reporting formats were standardized and used in all the states. Standard slide sets and training manuals for training of sentinel site personnel were developed centrally to ensure uniformity.
3. Trainings included group work and a “know your sentinel site” exercise, which helped participants to identify the routine practices that could affect the implementation of surveillance at their sites and recommended actions to address the same.
4. Pre and post-test assessments were given to each participant at the site-level trainings. Analysis of these scores helped state teams to identify the priority sites for supervisory visits.
5. Training reports for each batch were submitted in standard formats at the end of each training.

Details of trainings:

1. Trainings started with two batches of national pre-surveillance meetings with about 90 personnel from regional institutes and SACS to discuss the critical aspects of planning for HSS 2018-19 and to clearly understand the system for supportive supervision through the online Strategic Information Management System (SIMS) application.
2. This was followed by 2-day regional TOTs organised by the RIs for SACS officers and state surveillance teams, comprised of public health experts and microbiologists, to create state-level master trainers and to plan for the site-level trainings.
3. Site-level trainings (2 days per batch @ 8-10 sites per batch) were conducted in all the states. Representatives from the regional institutes and NACO observed the trainings to ensure that trainings were provided as per the protocol and that all the sessions were covered as per the session plan.
4. Separate trainings on surveillance testing protocols and lab reporting mechanisms through the SIMS application for HSS were organised for microbiologists and lab technicians from 117 ANC/STD testing labs and 13 NRLs.
5. Overall, 40 central team members; 30 officers from six RIs; 95 SACS officers including in-charge surveillance, Epidemiologists, and M&E officers; 280 state surveillance team members; 260 laboratory personnel including microbiologists and lab technicians from the designated testing labs; and more than 3,000 sentinel site personnel including medical officers, nurse/counsellors, and lab technicians were trained under HSS 2018-19.

Laboratory system:

- The laboratory system was strengthened by limiting the sample testing to designated SRLs.
- introduction of web based reporting through the SIMS application ensured real-time monitoring of the quality of blood specimens and laboratory processes
- Quality assurance aspects of sample testing under HSS were standardized
- Responses in case of discordant test results between testing lab and reference lab were streamlined through the SIMS application.

Supervisory mechanisms for HSS 2018-19:

- Supervision of all HSS activities was prioritized to ensure smooth implementation and high-quality data collection.
- Extensive mechanisms were developed to set up a comprehensive supervisory system for HSS and to ensure that 100 % of HSS sites were visited in the first 15 days of the start of sample collection.
- The principles adopted included action-oriented supervision, real-time monitoring and feedback, accountability for providing feedback and taking action, and an integrated web-based system to enhance the reach and effectiveness of supervision.

SIMS modules for web-based supervision:

- Specific modules were developed and made operational in the web-based SIMS for HSS to facilitate real-time monitoring of HSS 2018-19.
- Field supervision was conducted by trained supervisors who visited the sentinel sites to monitor the quality of recruitment of respondents and other site-level procedures. Real-time reporting of field supervision used the SIMS supervisor module via the field supervisory quick feedback and action taken report sub-modules. The module was used extensively by all the supervisors and helped in quick identification and resolution of challenges in the field.
- Data were supervised by data managers at RIs to monitor the quality of data collection and transportation using the SIMS module.
- Laboratory supervision was conducted by SRLs and NRLs to monitor the quality of blood specimens, progress in laboratory processing, and external quality assurance, using the SIMS lab module.
- Overall, 80 % of supervisors reported on the SIMS field supervisor quick feedback format, and 52 % of action taken report formats were submitted by HSS focal persons from SACS and RIs. Laboratory reporting through the lab module was completed by 87% of SRLs.

Integrated monitoring and supervision plan:

- An integrated supervision plan for each state was developed by RIs, SACS, and AIIMS to avoid duplication in monitoring coverage, thereby facilitating maximum coverage of surveillance sites.
- The first round of visits was conducted by RI, SACS, and SST members.
- Central team members (CTM) visited the top priority sites identified in feedback from the first round of visits.
- Subsequent visits were based on priority with a goal of making at least three visits to each identified site which require supervision.

2.3 Methodology of HSS at ANC Sentinel Sites:

The methodology for the 2019 round of HSS at ANC clinic attendees remained as same as the earlier round. The complete methodology may be found in the HIV Sentinel Surveillance Operational Guidelines available on the website of the National AIDS Control Organisation (NACO).

Figure 5: HSS Methodology

Table 2: Summary of HSS Methodology at ANC Sentinel Sites

Sentinel site	Antenatal clinic
Sample size	400
Duration	3 months
Frequency	Once in 2 years (biennial)
Sampling method	Consecutive sampling
Eligibility	Pregnant women ages 15-49 years attending ANC clinic for the first time during the current round
Testing strategy	Linked anonymous testing
Blood specimen	Serum collected through venous blood specimen
Testing protocol	Two-test

Key elements of the HSS methodology:

- In HSS among pregnant women, recruitment of respondents is conducted biennially for three months between January to March at selected ANC sentinel sites, across the nation.
- Because of the low HIV prevalence in India, the classical survey method of sample size calculation gives a large sample size. Owing to the practical difficulty in data and sample collection from such a large sample size through facility-based surveillance on regular basis, a sample size of 400 for surveillance among ANC attendees has been fixed.
- All eligible respondents are enrolled until the sample size of 400 in each sentinel site is reached or until the end of the surveillance period, whichever is earlier.
- Eligibility: All pregnant women eligible under the above inclusion criteria are included in the survey irrespective of the date of antenatal registration, known HIV positivity status, testing status under PPTCT programme or participation in the previous rounds of HSS.
- Inclusion Criteria: i. Age 15-49 years; ii. Pregnant woman attending the antenatal clinic for the first time during the current round of surveillance period
- Exclusion Criteria: i. Pregnant women not in the age group of 15-49 years; ii. Pregnant woman attending the antenatal clinic for the second or more time during the current round of surveillance period
- Sampling method, testing strategy and test protocol are standard components of any surveillance. Consecutive sampling method, linked anonymous testing strategy and two-test protocol are followed in HSS among pregnant women.

2.4 Information Collected under HSS at ANC Sentinel Sites

Information on 15 variables pertaining to the respondents' socio-demographic characteristics, HIV testing and management was collected. The data collected during the surveillance is robust and gives an insight on the socio-demographics and vulnerabilities of the respondents. The data helps the program managers and policy makers to identify of specific characteristics associated with higher risk of acquiring HIV infection. Thus the data has guided the HIV intervention program in responding to the epidemic effectively.

Figure 6: Recruitment process of ANC attendees at ANC Sentinel Sites for HSS

Figure 7: Information Collected under HSS at ANC Sentinel Sites

CHAPTER 3

PROFILE OF ANC ATTENDEES IN ANDHRA PRADESH

Andhra Pradesh (AP), situated at South-East India, shares its boundary with, Telangana and Karnataka in the West, Chhattisgarh and Odisha in the north-east, Tamil Nadu in the south, and the Bay of Bengal in the East. AP has 13 districts with a total area of 160,205 sq. km and a population of 49.67 million as per the 2011 census. The state of Andhra Pradesh was bifurcated to form the state of Telangana in 2014. AP was considered as one of the HIV high prevalent states in India, with the highest number of people living with AIDS (PLHIV) in India (5 lakh) during 2011-12. In 2004, AP recorded the highest prevalence of 1.91% among the antenatal clinic attendees. The pregnant women who attend the ANC clinics are considered proxy for general population and serve as a key indicator of the adult HIV prevalence. AP has implemented various programmes to bring down the HIV prevalence in the state. As a result, HIV prevalence among pregnant women which was 1.72% in 2002, has gradually declined to 0.30% in 2019.

Figure 8: HIV Prevalence Trend in Andhra Pradesh among ANC Attendees, 2002-19

The section presents findings from 2019 round of sentinel surveillance among the antenatal clinic attendees in Andhra Pradesh. First, the distribution of the respondents by their background characteristics has been presented by followed by HIV and Syphilis sero-positivity. Analysis of these variables is important because they help programme managers and policy makers understand the background characteristics of clinic attendees. Also they help in the identification of particular characteristics which make respondents more prone to acquiring HIV infection.

Table 3 : Distribution of the respondents by their background characteristics

Variables	Andhra Pradesh (N= 15600)	
	Number	%
Age		
15-24	11401	73.1
25-34	4093	26.2
35-44	104	0.7
45-49	2	0.0
literacy Status		
Illiterate	1827	11.7
Literate and till 5th standard	2465	15.8
6th to 10th standard	6122	39.2
11th to Graduation	4631	29.7
Post Graduation	541	3.5
Order of current pregnancy		
First	7199	46.1
Second	6330	40.6
Third	1628	10.4
Fourth or more	427	2.7
Duration of current pregnancy		
First trimester	3130	20.1
Second trimester	6223	39.9
Third trimester	6229	39.9
Received ANC service during current pregnancy		
Yes	11982	76.8
NO	3563	22.8
Source of referral to the ANC clinic		
Self Referral	2114	13.6
Family/ Relatives/ Neighbors/ Friends	4741	30.4
NGO	18	0.1
Private Hospital (Doctor/ Nurses)	804	5.2
Govt. Hospital (including, ASHA/ ANM)	7638	49.0
ICTC / ART Centre	265	1.7
Current place of residence		
Urban	4235	27.1
Rural	11155	71.5
Current occupation of the respondent		
Agricultural Labourer	1569	10.1
Non-Agricultural Labourer	776	5.0
Domestic Servant	23	0.1
Skilled / Semiskilled worker	121	0.8
Petty business / small shop	89	0.6
Large Business/Self employed	70	0.4
Service (Govt./Pvt.)	358	2.3
Student	124	0.8
Hotel staff	23	0.1
Truck driver/Helper		
Local transport worker (auto/taxi driver, hand cart pullers, rickshaw pullers etc)	1	0.0
Agricultural cultivator / landholder	202	1.3
Housewife	12237	78.4
Current occupation of the spouse		
Agricultural Labourer	3746	24.0
Non-Agricultural Labourer	3047	19.5
Domestic Servant	15	0.1

Skilled / Semiskilled worker	2199	14.1
Petty business / small shop	668	4.3
Large Business/Self employed	398	2.6
Service (Govt./Pvt.)	3088	19.8
Student	42	0.3
Hotel staff	149	1.0
Truck driver/Helper	463	3.0
Local transport worker (auto/taxi driver, hand cart pullers, rickshaw pullers etc)	1051	6.7
Agricultural cultivator / landholder	641	4.1
Unemployed	67	0.4
Not Applicable (For Never married/widows/Divorced/Separated)	8	0.1
Spouse resides alone in another place/town from wife for work for longer than 6 months		
Yes	257	1.6
No	15331	98.3
Not Applicable (For Never married/Widows/Divorced/ Separated)	8	0.1
Ever Been tested for HIV		
Yes	8741	56.0
No	6856	43.9
If ever tested HIV, When was the last tested		
Tested during current pregnancy	6100	39.1
Consented today	1	0.0
Tested before current pregnancy	2635	16.9
NA (For never tested)	6856	43.9
Result of respondent's last HIV test result		
Positive	23	0.1
Negative	8693	55.7
Did not collect the last result	23	0.1
No response	2	0.01
NA (For never tested/Consented today))	6856	43.9
If previous HIV test positive, taking ART medications		
Yes	22	0.1
No	1	0.01
NA (never tested or Not positive when last tested/Consented today)	15574	99.8
HIV		
Negative	15553	99.7
Positive	47	0.30
Syphilis		
Negative	15600	100
Positive		

CHAPTER 4

DISTRIBUTION AND HIV PREVALENCE BY SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES

The correlation between respondent's background characteristics and HIV prevalence has been presented.

4.1 Distribution and HIV Prevalence by Age Group:

Figure 9: Percentage (%) Distribution of respondents by age group

Figure 10: HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Age

Age of the respondents ranged from 15 to 44 years with a median age of 24 years. More than two-thirds (73.1%) of the respondents were aged from 15 to 24 years and about one-fourth (26.2%) were in the age group of 25-34 years. The HIV prevalence among the former was 0.28% and the later was 0.34%. While only 0.7% respondents belonged to the age group of 35-44 years, HIV prevalence among them was 0.96%. None of the respondents belonged to the age group of 45-49 years.

4.2 Distribution and HIV Prevalence by Literacy Status

Figure 11: Percent Distribution of respondents by educational status

Figure 12: HIV Prevalence (%) among ANC Clinic Attendees by Literacy Status

While over one-third (36.3%) had secondary level education, about 29.7% of the respondents had higher secondary or undergraduate level of education. The HIV prevalence among the former was 0.33% and the later was 0.22%. While about one-tenth (11.7%) were illiterates, 15.8% were educated up to primary levels, and only 3.5% were post-graduates. The HIV prevalence among them was 0.49%, 0.32% and 0% respectively. Predominantly, higher the standard of education level, lower was the HIV prevalence.

4.3 Distribution and HIV Prevalence by Order of Pregnancy

Figure 13: Percent Distribution of respondents by order of pregnancy

Figure 14: HIV Prevalence (%) among ANC Clinic Attendees by Order of Pregnancy

The order of pregnancy, also known as gravida, is the number of times a woman had become pregnant including live births, still births and abortions. About 46.19% of the respondents were in their first gravida, 40.68% in their second and 10.42% in their third with a prevalence of 0.32%, 0.25% and 0.37% respectively. Other higher order pregnancies were only 2.71% with a prevalence of 0.47%.

4.4 Distribution and HIV Prevalence by Duration of Pregnancy:

Figure 15: Percent Distribution of respondents by duration of current pregnancy

Figure 16: HIV Prevalence (%) among ANC Clinic Attendees by Duration of Pregnancy

One-fifth of the respondents (20.12%) belonged to the first trimester followed by 30.86% in second trimester and 39.94% in the third trimester. However, highest HIV prevalence (0.48%) was recorded among respondents in first trimester, followed by 0.29% in third and 0.22% in second trimesters.

4.5 Distribution and HIV Prevalence by ANC Service Utilization :

Figure 17: Percent Distribution of respondents by order of pregnancy

Figure 18: HIV Prevalence (%) among ANC Clinic Attendees by Order of Pregnancy

This refers to any prior receipt of antenatal care services from a health care facility (PHC/CHC/District hospitals/Maternity hospitals/Private health care facilities/NGO Health care facilities) by the pregnant women during her current pregnancy. In Andhra Pradesh, about 77.11% of respondents had received ANC services during current pregnancy prior to the surveillance whereas 22.89% of respondents had not received prior ANC services. HIV prevalence was 0.29% and 0.31% among respondents who had and had not received prior ANC services, respectively.

4.6 Distribution and HIV Prevalence by Source of Referral :

Figure 19: Percent Distribution of respondents by source of referral

Figure 20: HIV Prevalence (%) among ANC Clinic Attendees by Source of Referral

Knowing the sources of referral helps to identify referral bias being introduced in the sample due to specific referrals of HIV-positive cases from any source. Government based sources including hospital, ANM/ASHA were identified as the major referral source (49.0%) to ANC clinics, followed by family/relatives/ neighbour/friends (30.4%) and self-referral (13.6%). Highest HIV prevalence (0.75%) was recorded in respondents referred by ICTC/ART centres although the proportion referred accounted to only 1.7%. This was followed by referral through friends and relatives (0.34%) and self-referral (0.34%). While prevalence among referrals from government hospitals was 0.27% that of the private was 0.12%.

4.7 Distribution and HIV Prevalence by Place of Residence:

Figure 21: Percent Distribution of respondents by current place of residence

Figure 22: HIV Prevalence (%) among ANC Clinic Attendees by Place of residence

Current residence of the respondent was recorded either as urban or rural. Areas under municipal corporation, municipal council, or cantonment area, were classified as urban and the rest were classified as rural. At the state level, 68.8 % of the respondents reported to be currently residing in rural areas and the rest (34.9%) reported to be currently residing in urban areas. However, there were inter-district variations. HIV prevalence among the urban-resident respondents was 0.18%; whereas it was 0.17% among the rural-resident respondents.

4.8 Distribution and HIV Prevalence by Occupation of the Respondent:

Figure 23: District-wise % Distribution of respondents by Occupation

Figure 24: HIV Prevalence (%) among ANC Clinic Attendees by Current Occupation of Respondent

Certain occupations are associated with higher risk of exposure and HIV infection. Hence, understanding the profile of respondents with respect to their occupation, helps to identify specific focus areas. While a vast majority of them were housewives, about 10.1% were agricultural labourers and 5.0% were non-agricultural labourers. In Andhra Pradesh, the highest HIV prevalence was recorded among pregnant mothers whose current occupation was non-agricultural labourers (0.52%) followed by housewives (0.33%) and agricultural labourers (0.19%).

4.9 Distribution and HIV Prevalence by Occupation of the Respondents' Spouse:

HIV transmission in South India is mainly driven through heterosexual route and pregnant mothers represent the sexually active population. Hence occupation of spouse serves to identify population groups at higher infection risk. The occupation of spouses of nearly one-fourth of ANC corresponded to agricultural labourers (24.0%), followed by service sector (19.8%), non-agricultural labourers (19.5%) and skilled/semi-skilled workers (14.1%). While 6.7% were local transport workers, 3.0% were truckers. The proportion spouses of ANC mothers who were petty or small business owners was 4.3% agricultural cultivators was 4.1%, large business owners/self-employed was 2.6% and hotel staffs was 1.0%. HIV prevalence was the highest among the ANC attendees whose spouses were truckers (0.86%) followed by hotel staffs (0.67%), large business owners/self-employed (0.50%) and local transport workers (0.48%). The prevalence ranged from 0.13% to 0.41% among respondents whose spouses were agricultural / non-agricultural labourers, agricultural cultivators, skilled or semi-skilled workers, petty / small shop owners and service sector employees.

Figure 25: % Distribution of respondents by the Occupation of spouse

Figure 26: HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Current Occupation of Spouse

4.10 Distribution and HIV Prevalence by Migration Status of the Respondents' Spouse:

The spouse of the respondent is considered to be a migrant if he resides alone in another place or town away from wife for work for longer than 6 months. In TN, during HSS 2019, 98.3% of the pregnant women reported their husbands to be non-migrants while the spouses of 1.6% pregnant women were migrants. While the HIV prevalence among pregnant women with migrant spouses was 0.39%, that of the pregnant women with non-migrant spouses was 0.30%.

Figure 27: Percentage of respondents with migrant spouse

Figure 28: HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Migration status of Spouse

4.11 Distribution and HIV Prevalence by HIV Test History:

Figure 29: Percent Distribution of respondents by HIV testing history

Figure 30: HIV Prevalence by HIV Test History

HIV Testing has been mandated for all pregnant mothers. With reference to their previous HIV test history, 56.0% of the respondents were already tested for HIV, prior to the current surveillance. HIV prevalence among those who had previously tested for HIV was 0.38% and it was 0.20% among those who had previously not tested for HIV

Among the respondents, 39.14% had tested for HIV prior to the surveillance during current pregnancy while 16.92% had tested before current pregnancy. About 43.9% had not tested for HIV. Of the 56.0% respondents who had last tested for HIV, prior to the current surveillance, 55.7% were HIV Negative, 0.1% were HIV positive, 0.1% had not collected the results of the last HIV test; and 0.01% had no response.

Figure 31: Percent Distribution of respondents by Time of last HIV Testing

Figure 32: HIV prevalence by Result of last HIV test

4.12 Distribution and HIV Prevalence by HIV Management:

Based on the result of the last HIV test of the respondents, 23 pregnant women were reported to be known-positives. HIV management related information was gathered from known-positive respondents. With reference to the enrolment of HIV positive respondents in any HIV care, either for pre-ART or ART services, at the time of surveillance, 100% (n=23) of them, were taking care from Government hospital/ART centres. With reference to the current uptake of 'Antiretroviral therapy' or HIV medications, 95.7% (n=22) of them, were taking ART or HIV medications, whereas 4.3% (n=1) were not taking any HIV medications.

CHAPTER 5

5.1 District-wise Distribution of Respondents, HIV Prevalence and Trend

The national, state and district response to the HIV epidemic is guided by data obtained through HIV Sentinel Surveillance (HSS). The HIV epidemic in India continues to be concentrated among HRG with low level and declining prevalence among general population. Over time, HIV Sentinel Surveillance has offered vital clues to newer areas where HIV was emerging, highlighting rising trends in certain districts or regions.

This chapter gives district-wise distribution of respondents, HIV prevalence and its trend details as observed against the key fifteen socio-demographic variables which were recorded for each respondent. Data from the year 2002 has been used for trend analysis. Data from only consistent sites was used for trend analysis as it avoids the effect of addition of new sites on HIV prevalence in subsequent years, and hence provides a better picture of HIV trends in a district. Though there was a clear declining trend seen in Andhra Pradesh, within the state, there are variations in HIV prevalence among the districts. A detailed district-wise analysis by applying local knowledge about vulnerabilities and risk factors, will be needed to understand heterogeneity of the disease and inter-district variations, which is essential for planning district strategies in HIV prevention and control.

Figure 33 : District-wise HIV Prevalence in Andhra Pradesh, 2019

Figure 34 : Spatial Representation of district-wise HIV Prevalence in Andhra Pradesh, 2019

Table 4: District-wise distribution of respondents based on the age group (%)

Age Group	15-24	25-34	35-44	45-49	Total
Andhra Pradesh	73.1	26.2	0.7	0	15600
Anantapur	68.4	30.8	0.8	0	1600
Chittoor	69.4	29.9	0.7	0	1200
Cuddapah	65.8	33.1	1.1	0	800
East Godavari	75.9	23.8	0.3	0	1200
Guntur	79.1	20.1	0.8	0	1200
Krishna	72.5	26.6	0.9	0	1200
Kurnool	73.6	25.7	0.8	0	1200
Nellore	77.0	22.3	0.7	0	1200
Prakasam	78.6	20.8	0.6	0	1200
Srikakulam	76.6	23.0	0.4	0	800
Visakhapatnam	59.5	39.5	0.9	0.1	1600
Vizianagaram	78.7	20.8	0.5	0	1200
West Godavari	79.9	19.9	0.2	0	1200

Table 5: District-wise distribution of respondents based on the literacy status(%)

State/District	Illiterate	Literate				N
		and till 5th standard	6th to 10th standard	11th to Graduation	Post Graduation	
Andhra Pradesh	11.7	15.8	39.3	29.7	3.5	15600
Anantapur	8.4	28.1	40.3	21.3	1.8	1600
Chittoor	7.3	9.5	39.5	37.9	5.8	1200
Cuddapah	24.9	27.0	30.1	16.8	1.3	800
East Godavari	5.7	7.5	52.6	32.5	1.6	1200
Guntur	17.2	13.6	45.3	21.3	2.7	1200
Krishna	5.2	7.4	44.8	36.1	6.5	1200
Kurnool	22.9	22.4	33.2	19.6	2.0	1200
Nellore	11.5	31.7	41.7	13.4	1.7	1200
Prakasam	18.2	16.2	41.0	21.4	3.3	1200
Srikakulam	5.3	15.3	36.0	42.8	0.8	800
Visakhapatnam	12.6	4.7	26.6	48.3	7.7	1600
Vizianagaram	9.8	11.3	34.5	40.2	4.2	1200
West Godavari	6.5	14.0	44.8	31.3	3.4	1200

Table 6: District-wise distribution of respondents based on the Order of Pregnancy (%)

State/District	First	Second	Third	Fourth or more	N
Andhra Pradesh	46.1	40.6	10.4	2.7	15600
Anantapur	32.6	51.7	11.9	3.7	1600
Chittoor	47.3	39.3	11.6	1.7	1200
Cuddapah	40.9	47.5	8.4	3.1	800
East Godavari	51.0	37.1	9.8	2.0	1200
Guntur	44.1	39.4	13.0	3.3	1200
Krishna	52.8	38.6	7.0	1.7	1200
Kurnool	44.5	33.3	16.7	5.6	1200
Nellore	41.3	44.8	12.4	1.5	1200
Prakasam	41.3	39.8	14.6	4.3	1200
Srikakulam	49.6	42.8	5.5	2.1	800
Visakhapatnam	51.3	33.8	10.6	3.9	1600
Vizianagaram	52.8	40.7	5.8	0.8	1200
West Godavari	52.8	40.5	5.6	1.1	1200

Table 7: District-wisedistribution of respondents based on the Duration of Pregnancy(%)

State/District	First trimester	Second trimester	Third trimester	N
Andhra Pradesh	20.06	39.89	39.93	15600
Anantapur	29.1	50.7	19.9	1600
Chittoor	36.7	38.4	24.8	1200
Cuddapah	9.9	57.8	32.4	800
East Godavari	15.3	32.1	52.4	1200
Guntur	21.4	34.8	43.7	1200
Krishna	15.3	38.4	46.3	1200
Kurnool	10.7	32.3	57.0	1200
Nellore	23.8	38.4	37.7	1200
Prakasam	17.7	37.2	45.2	1200
Srikakulam	13.1	31.4	55.4	800
Visakhapatnam	29.3	42.4	28.0	1600
Vizianagaram	12.5	41.3	46.3	1200
West Godavari	14.3	42.1	43.4	1200

Table 8 : District-wise distribution of respondents based on the Prior ANC service uptake

State/District	Yes	No	N
Andhra Pradesh	76.8	22.8	15600
Anantapur	51.3	48.6	1600
Chittoor	71.6	28.2	1200
Cuddapah	46.5	53.5	800
East Godavari	84.7	14.8	1200
Guntur	65.0	34.7	1200
Krishna	97.0	2.7	1200
Kurnool	91.5	8.2	1200
Nellore	60.6	39.1	1200
Prakasam	86.8	12.9	1200
Srikakulam	86.9	12.5	800
Visakhapatnam	81.0	18.5	1600
Vizianagaram	91.8	8.1	1200
West Godavari	84.2	15.0	1200

Table 9: District-wise distribution of respondents based on the Source of Referral

State/District	Self Referral	Family/ Relatives/ Neighbors/ Friends	NGO	Private (Doctor/ Nurses)	Govt (including, ASHA/ ANM)	ICTC / ART Centre	N
Andhra Pradesh	13.6	30.4	0.1	5.2	49.0	1.7	15600
Anantapur	30.8	13.7	0.6	0.9	53.9	0.0	1600
Chittoor	6.7	10.5	0.0	33.3	49.3	0.2	1200
Cuddapah	3.8	11.6	0.0	0.6	83.5	0.0	800
East Godavari	18.2	59.8	0.1	0.6	21.3	0.0	1200
Guntur	38.4	27.8	0.1	0.1	33.7	0.0	1200
Krishna	2.4	63.6	0.0	0.0	33.9	0.0	1200
Kurnool	5.2	39.3	0.0	0.8	54.5	0.0	1200
Nellore	5.0	36.3	0.1	0.0	36.6	21.8	1200
Prakasam	14.1	47.8	0.0	1.8	36.1	0.2	1200
Srikakulam	2.0	17.0	0.1	0.0	80.9	0.0	800
Visakhapatnam	22.2	26.4	0.3	6.6	44.3	0.0	1600
Vizianagaram	6.9	13.8	0.0	1.3	78.0	0.0	1200
West Godavari	4.8	23.6	0.0	18.8	52.8	0.0	1200

Table 10: District-wise distribution of respondents based on Place of Residence

State/District	Urban	Rural	N
Andhra Pradesh	27.1	71.5	15600
Anantapur	32.2	66.5	1600
Chittoor	31.3	66.3	1200
Cuddapah	30.9	68.5	800
East Godavari	12.8	85.2	1200
Guntur	19.9	79.3	1200
Krishna	40.0	59.8	1200
Kurnool	31.9	67.7	1200
Nellore	26.3	72.3	1200
Prakasam	22.3	76.9	1200
Srikakulam	7.9	89.9	800
Visakhapatnam	46.1	51.3	1600
Vizianagaram	24.6	74.8	1200
West Godavari	13.7	84.8	1200

Table 11: District-wise distribution of respondents based on the Occupation (%)

State/District	Agricultural Labourer	Non-Agricultural Labourer	Domestic Servant	Skilled / Semiskilled worker	Petty business / small shop	Large Business/Self employed	Service (Govt./Pvt.)	Student	Hotel staff	Truck driver/Helper	Local transport Worker	Agricultural cultivator	Housewife	Total
Andhra Pradesh	10.1	5.0	0.1	0.8	0.6	0.4	2.3	0.8	0.1	0.0	0.0	1.3	78.4	15600
Anantapur	9.2	18.8	0.4	1.6	2.0	2.7	4.8	1.8	0.7	0.0	0.1	1.4	56.5	1600
Chittoor	5.8	0.6	0.0	0.2	0.8	0.2	2.4	0.3	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	89.6	1200
Cuddapah	13.8	7.4	0.0	1.5	1.5	0.5	1.9	0.5	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.3	72.6	800
East Godavari	2.1	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	1.3	0.3	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.4	95.3	1200
Guntur	11.1	12.8	0.1	0.4	0.3	0.1	1.9	0.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	72.4	1200
Krishna	1.3	0.2	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.2	1.8	0.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	95.9	1200
Kurnool	15.0	1.5	0.3	2.3	0.6	0.6	0.8	0.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	11.3	66.9	1200
Nellore	18.9	6.0	0.5	1.2	0.5	0.0	3.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	69.4	1200
Prakasam	8.0	6.6	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.3	1.1	0.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	82.8	1200
Srikakulam	2.1	7.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	89.8	800
Visakhapatnam	22.8	0.6	0.1	0.8	0.8	0.4	5.9	2.0	0.6	0.0	0.0	0.1	65.9	1600
Vizianagaram	6.5	0.7	0.0	0.5	0.3	0.1	0.8	1.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.8	87.1	1200
West Godavari	8.9	0.6	0.0	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.8	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	88.8	1200

Table 12: District-wise distribution of respondents based on the Occupation of spouse

State/District	Agricultural Labourer	Non-Agricultural Labourer	Domestic Servant	Skilled / Semiskilled worker	Petty business / small shop	Large Business/Self employed	Service (Govt./Pvt.)	Student	Hotel staff	Truck driver/Helper	Local transport Worker	Agricultural cultivator	Unemployed	Not Applicable	Total
Andhra Pradesh	24.0	19.5	0.1	14.1	4.3	2.6	19.8	0.3	1.0	3.0	6.7	4.1	0.4	0.1	15600
Anantapur	21.1	26.8	0.6	8.8	4.6	4.5	16.9	0.3	1.6	4.2	5.8	3.8	0.9	0.1	1600
Chittoor	28.6	6.8	0.0	16.6	7.5	3.7	19.0	0.3	1.2	3.5	6.3	6.4	0.0	0.0	1200
Cuddapah	16.5	14.1	0.1	29.3	4.3	4.4	9.6	0.1	0.6	2.5	13.8	4.5	0.3	0.0	800
East Godavari	35.3	14.1	0.2	18.5	3.7	1.3	16.7	0.0	1.0	1.6	5.3	2.0	0.6	0.0	1200
Guntur	24.3	31.0	0.0	11.9	3.8	1.4	17.1	0.4	0.8	1.8	6.4	0.4	0.6	0.0	1200
Krishna	26.0	8.0	0.0	14.8	3.7	6.0	29.6	0.2	0.7	3.0	7.2	0.1	0.5	0.3	1200
Kurnool	17.3	10.0	0.0	18.7	5.3	2.1	13.3	0.6	0.8	2.8	9.1	19.4	0.4	0.1	1200
Nellore	26.2	23.0	0.0	16.8	5.0	1.5	12.8	0.1	0.9	4.3	8.2	1.1	0.0	0.1	1200
Prakasam	19.0	35.3	0.0	12.3	4.3	1.4	14.7	0.3	0.4	2.3	8.7	1.3	0.3	0.0	1200
Srikakulam	22.6	37.9	0.0	9.3	3.6	0.5	20.0	0.1	0.1	0.3	5.1	0.0	0.3	0.0	800
Visakhapatnam	25.0	14.5	0.2	4.4	4.1	2.6	36.8	0.7	1.4	5.2	2.8	1.4	0.8	0.1	1600
Vizianagaram	10.3	13.1	0.0	14.3	4.3	2.6	32.1	0.3	1.6	2.3	6.0	12.7	0.5	0.0	1200
West Godavari	37.7	23.1	0.0	16.2	1.3	0.6	10.8	0.0	0.6	2.8	6.5	0.2	0.1	0.0	1200

Table 13: District -wise distribution of respondents based on Migration of Spouse

State/District	Yes	No	Not Applicable	N
Andhra Pradesh	1.6	98.3	0.1	15600
Anantapur	2.8	97.1	0.1	1600
Chittoor	4.3	95.7	0	1200
Cuddapah	0.4	99.6	0	800
East Godavari	0.6	99.4	0	1200
Guntur	1.4	98.5	0	1200
Krishna	0.1	99.6	0.3	1200
Kurnool	0.8	99.1	0.1	1200
Nellore	2.2	97.7	0.1	1200
Prakasam	6.1	93.9	0	1200
Srikakulam	0.6	99.4	0	800
Visakhapatnam	0.1	99.8	0.1	1600
Vizianagaram	1.0	99.0	0	1200
West Godavari	0.3	99.6	0	1200

Table 14: District wise distribution of respondents based on HIV tested history

State/District	Yes	No	N
Andhra Pradesh	56.0	43.9	15600
Anantapur	47.8	52.3	1600
Chittoor	33.9	66.1	1200
Cuddapah	40.3	59.8	800
East Godavari	71.4	28.6	1200
Guntur	36.2	63.8	1200
Krishna	87.7	12.3	1200
Kurnool	45.2	54.8	1200
Nellore	58.6	41.3	1200
Prakasam	65.2	34.8	1200
Srikakulam	39.4	60.6	800
Visakhapatnam	72.1	27.9	1600
Vizianagaram	65.9	34.1	1200
West Godavari	51.6	48.3	1200

**Table 15: District-wise distribution of respondents based on the Time of their last HIV test
(Only the respondent whom tested for HIV test previously)**

State/District	Tested previously during current pregnancy	Consented today	Tested before current pregnancy	Total
Andhra Pradesh	69.79	0.01	30.15	8741
Anantapur	94.37	0.00	5.63	764
Chittoor	79.36	0.00	20.64	407
Cuddapah	84.47	0.00	15.53	322
East Godavari	64.64	0.00	35.36	857
Guntur	58.29	0.23	41.47	434
Krishna	76.14	0.00	23.86	1052
Kurnool	61.99	0.00	38.01	542
Nellore	42.39	0.00	57.61	703
Prakasam	95.01	0.00	4.99	782
Srikakulam	40.32	0.00	59.68	315
Visakhapatnam	64.18	0.00	35.39	1153
Vizianagaram	78.00	0.00	22.00	791
West Godavari	50.89	0.00	49.11	619

**Table 16: District wise distribution of respondents based on the HIV test results(%)
(Only the respondent whom tested for HIV test previously)**

State/District	Positive	Negative	Did not collect the test result	No Response	Total
Andhra Pradesh	0.26	99.45	0.26	0.02	8741
Anantapur	0.26	97.64	2.09	0.00	764
Chittoor	0.98	99.02	0.00	0.00	407
Cuddapah	0.31	98.76	0.93	0.00	322
East Godavari	0.47	99.30	0.00	0.23	857
Guntur	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	434
Krishna	0.19	99.81	0.00	0.00	1052
Kurnool	0.18	99.82	0.00	0.00	542
Nellore	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	703
Prakasam	0.26	99.62	0.13	0.00	782
Srikakulam	0.32	99.68	0.00	0.00	315
Visakhapatnam	0.35	99.48	0.17	0.00	1153
Vizianagaram	0.13	99.75	0.13	0.00	791
West Godavari	0.16	99.84	0.00	0.00	619

Table 17: District -wise distribution of respondents based on the HIV management

State/District	ART	NGO	Pvt	Pharmacist/	Alternative/ non Allopathic	Any other type	Not seeking taking for HIV management	Total
Andhra Pradesh	23							23
Anantapur	2							2
Chittoor	4							4
Cuddapah	1							1
East Godavari	4							4
Krishna	2							2
Kurnool	1							1
Prakasam	2							2
Srikakulam	1							1
Visakhapatnam	4							4
Vizianagaram	1							1
West Godavari	1							1

Table 18: District -wise distribution of HIV positive respondents based on the ART uptake (%)

(Results Only;If respondent whom Previous HIV test results positive and ART taken currently or not)

State/District	1. Yes	2. No	Total
Andhra Pradesh	95.7	4.3	23
Anantapur	100	0	2
Chittoor	100	0	4
Cuddapah	100	0	1
East Godavari	100	0	4
Krishna	100	0	2
Kurnool	0.0	100.0	1
Prakasam	100	0	2
Srikakulam	100	0	1
Visakhapatnam	100	0	4
Vizianagaram	100	0	1
West Godavari	100	0	1

Table 19: HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Age

State/Districts	15-24		25-34		35-44		45-49 Total		Total
	%	Total	%	Total	%	Total	%	Total	
Andhra Pradesh	0.28	11401	0.34	4093	0.96	104	0	2	15600
Anantapur	0.46	1094	0.41	493	0	13			1600
Chittoor	0.60	833	0.56	359	0	8			1200
Cuddapah	0.19	526	0	265	0	9			800
East Godavari	0.44	911	0.70	285	0	4			1200
Guntur	0.21	949	0	241	0	10			1200
Krishna	0	870	0.94	319	0	11			1200
Kurnool	0.11	883	0.32	308	0	9			1200
Nellore	0.32	924	0	268	0	8			1200
Prakasam	0.32	943	0	250	0	7			1200
Srikakulam	0.16	613	0	184	0	3			800
Visakhapatnam	0.32	952	0.16	632	0	14	0	2	1600
Vizianagaram	0.21	944	0.40	250	0	6			1200
West Godavari	0.21	959	0.84	239	50.00	2			1200

Table 20: HIV Prevalence (%) among ANC Clinic Attendees by Literacy Status and Districts

State/District	1. Illiterate		2. Literate and till 5th standard		3. 6th to 10th standard		4. 11th to Graduation		5. Post Graduation		N
	%	Total	%	Total	%	Total	%	Total	%	Total	
	Andhra Pradesh	0.49	1827	0.32	2465	0.33	6122	0.22	4631	0	
Anantapur	2.96	135	0.44	450	0.16	644	0	341	0	29	1600
Chittoor	0	87	0.88	114	0.84	474	0.44	455	0	70	1200
Cuddapah	0	199	0	216	0.41	241	0	134	0	10	800
East Godavari	0	68	0	90	0.80	628	0.26	388	0	19	1200
Guntur	0	206	0	163	0.37	543	0	256	0	32	1200
Krishna	0	62	0	89	0.19	537	0.46	433	0	78	1200
Kurnool	0	274	0.75	268	0	398	0	235	0	24	1200
Nellore	1.45	138	0	380	0	500	0.62	161	0	20	1200
Prakasam	0.46	218	0.52	194	0	492	0.39	257	0	39	1200
Srikakulam	0	42	0	122	0	288	0.29	342	0	6	800
Visakhapatnam	0.50	202	0	75	0.71	425	0	772	0	123	1600
Vizianagaram	0	118	0.74	136	0.48	414	0	482	0	50	1200
West Godavari	1.28	78	0.60	168	0.19	538	0.53	375	0	41	1200

Table 21: HIV Prevalence (%) among ANC Clinic Attendees by Order of Pregnancy and districts

State/District	First		2. Second		3. Third		4. Fourth or more		Total
	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	
Andhra Pradesh	0.32	7199	0.25	6330	0.37	1628	0.47	427	15600
Anantapur	0.57	522	0.24	827	0.52	191	1.69	59	1600
Chittoor	0.70	568	0.42	472	0	139	5.00	20	1200
Cuddapah	0.31	327	0	380	0	67	0	25	800
East Godavari	0.49	612	0.67	445	0	117	0	24	1200
Guntur	0.19	529	0	473	0.64	156	0	40	1200
Krishna	0.32	633	0.22	463	0	84	0	20	1200
Kurnool	0.19	534	0.25	399	0	200	0	67	1200
Nellore	0	495	0.37	537	0.67	149	0	18	1200
Prakasam	0	495	0.63	477	0	175	0	51	1200
Srikakulam	0.25	397	0	342	0	44	0	17	800
Visakhapatnam	0.24	820	0	541	1.18	170	0	63	1600
Vizianagaram	0.32	633	0.20	488	0	69	0	10	1200
West Godavari	0.47	634	0.21	486	1.49	67	0	13	1200

Table 22: HIV Prevalence (%) among ANC Clinic Attendees by Duration of Pregnancy and districts

State/District	First trimester		Second trimester		Third trimester		Total
	%	N	%	N	%	N	
Andhra Pradesh	0.48	3130	0.22	6223	0.29	6229	15600
Anantapur	1.29	466	0.12	811	0	319	1600
Chittoor	0.23	440	0.65	461	1.01	298	1200
Cuddapah	0	79	0	462	0.39	259	800
East Godavari	1.09	184	0	385	0.64	629	1200
Guntur	0.39	257	0.24	418	0	524	1200
Krishna	0	184	0.43	461	0.18	555	1200
Kurnool	0	128	0.26	388	0.15	684	1200
Nellore	0.70	285	0	461	0.22	452	1200
Prakasam	0	212	0.22	446	0.37	542	1200
Srikakulam	0	105	0.40	251	0	443	800
Visakhapatnam	0.43	468	0.15	679	0.22	448	1600
Vizianagaram	0	150	0.40	495	0.18	555	1200
West Godavari	0.58	172	0.20	505	0.58	521	1200

Table 23: HIV Prevalence (%) among ANC Clinic Attendees by ANC service uptake and districts

State/District	Yes		No		Total
	%	N	%	N	
Andhra Pradesh	0.29	11982	0.31	3563	15600
Anantapur	0.49	821	0.39	777	1600
Chittoor	0.70	859	0.30	338	1200
Cuddapah	0.27	372	0	428	800
East Godavari	0.39	1016	0.56	177	1200
Guntur	0.13	780	0.24	416	1200
Krishna	0.26	1164	0	32	1200
Kurnool	0.18	1098	0	98	1200
Nellore	0.14	727	0.43	469	1200
Prakasam	0.29	1042	0	155	1200
Srikakulam	0.14	695	0	100	800
Visakhapatnam	0.23	1296	0.34	296	1600
Vizianagaram	0.18	1102	1.03	97	1200
West Godavari	0.40	1010	0.56	180	1200

Table 24 : Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Place of Residence and district

State/District	Urban		Rural		Total
	%	N	%	N	
Andhra Pradesh	0.35	4235	0.29	11155	15600
Anantapur	0.78	515	0.28	1064	1600
Chittoor	0.80	376	0.50	795	1200
Cuddapah	0	247	0.18	548	800
East Godavari	0.65	153	0.49	1022	1200
Guntur	0.42	239	0.11	951	1200
Krishna	0.42	480	0.14	718	1200
Kurnool	0	383	0.25	812	1200
Nellore	0.32	315	0.23	867	1200
Prakasam	0.37	268	0.22	923	1200
Srikakulam	0	63	0.14	719	800
Visakhapatnam	0.14	737	0.37	821	1600
Vizianagaram	0	295	0.33	898	1200
West Godavari	0.61	164	0.39	1017	1200

Table 25 : HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Current Occupation of Respondent

State/District	Agricultural Labourer		Non-Agricultural Labourer		Domestic Servant		Skilled / Semiskilled worker		Petty business / small shop		Large Business/self employed		Service (Govt./Pvt.)		Student		Hotel staff		Local transportWorker cultivator/		Housewife		Grand Total	
	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N
Andhra Pradesh	0.19	1569	0.52	776	0.00	23	0.00	121	0.00	89	0.00	70	0.00	358	0.00	124	0.00	23	1	0.00	202	0.33	12237	15600
Anantapur	0	147	0.66	301	0.00	7	0.00	26	0.00	32	43	0.00	77	29	11	1	0.00	22	0.55	904	1600			
Chittoor	0	70	0.00	7	0.00	2	0.00	9	2	0.00	29	4	1	1	1	0.65	1075	1200						
Cuddapah	0	110	0.00	59	0.00	12	0.00	12	4	0.00	15	4	1	1	0.00	581	800							
East Godavari	0	25	0.00	3	0.00	1	0.00	1	3	0.00	16	3	1	1	0.00	5	0.52	1144	1200					
Guntur	0	133	0.00	153	0.00	1	0.00	4	1	0.00	23	9	1	0.00	1	0.23	869	1200						
Krishna	0	15	0.00	2	0.00	3	2	0.00	22	5	0.26	1151	1200											
Kurnool	0	180	0.00	18	0.00	4	0.00	27	0.00	7	7	0.00	10	9	0.00	135	0.25	803	1200					
Nellore	0.44	227	1.39	72	0.00	6	0.00	14	0.00	6	4	0.00	36	4	0.12	833	1200							
Prakasam	0	96	0.00	79	0.00	2	0.00	4	0.00	3	3	0.00	13	5	0.00	1	0.30	994	1200					
Srikakulam	0	17	0.00	58	0.00	4	0.00	2	0.00	4	0.00	4	2	0.00	1	0.14	718	800						
Visakhapatnam	0.55	364	11.11	9	0.00	2	0.00	13	0.00	12	7	0.00	95	32	9	0.00	1	0.09	1054	1600				
Vizianagaram	0	78	0.00	8	0.00	3	0.00	6	0.00	3	1	0.00	9	16	0.00	34	0.29	1045	1200					
West Godavari	0	107	0.00	7	0.00%	8	0.00	9	2	0.47	1066	1200												

* no respondents reported under truck driver/helper categories

Table 2.6: HIV Prevalence (%) among ANC Clinic Attendees by Source of Referral

State/District	1. Self Referral		2. Family/ Relatives/ Neighbors/ Friends		3. NGO		4. Private (Doctor/ Nurses)		5. Govt (including, ASHA/ ANM)		6. ICTC / ART Centre		Total
	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	
Andhra Pradesh	0.33	2114	0.34	4741	0	18	0.12	804	0.27	7638	0.75	265	15600
Anantapur	0.41	493	0.91	219	0	10	0	15	0.35	863			1600
Chittoor	0	80	0.79	126			0	400	0.85	591	50.00	2	1200
Cuddapah	0	30	0	93			0	5	0.15	668			800
East Godavari	0.92	218	0.28	718	0	1	0	7	0.78	255			1200
Guntur	0.22	461	0.30	333	0	1	0	1	0	404			1200
Krishna	0	29	0.13	763					0.49	407			1200
Kurnool	0	62	0	472			0	10	0.31	654			1200
Nellore	1.67	60	0.23	436	0	1			0	439	0.38	261	1200
Prakasam	0	169	0.52	574			0	21	0	433	0	2	1200
Srikakulam	0	16	0.74	136	0	1			0	647			800
Visakhapatnam	0	355	0.24	422	0	4	0	105	0.42	708			1600
Vizianagaram	1.20	83	0	166			0	15	0.21	936			1200
West Godavari	0	58	1.06	283			0.44	225	0.16	633			1200

Table 27: HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Current Occupation of Spouse

State/District	Agricultural Labourer		Non-Agricultural Labourer		Domestic Servant		Skilled / Semiskilled worker		Petty business / small shop		Large Business/Self employed		Service (Govt./Pvt.)		Student		Hotel staff		Truck driver/Helper		Local transport Worker		Agricultural cultivator		Unemployed		Not Applicable		Total	
	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N
Andhra Pradesh	0.13	3746	0.39	3047	0	15	0.41	2199	0.3	668	0.5	398	0.16	3088	0	42	0.67	149	0.86	463	0.48	1051	0.31	641	0	67	0	8	15600	
Anantapur	0	338	0.7	428	9	9	0	141	1.35	74	1.39	72	0	270	4	4	0	25	0	67	1.8	93	1.64	61	14	0	1	1600		
Chittoor	0.29	343	1.23	81			0.5	199	0	90	0	44	0.44	228	4	4	0	14	2.38	42	2.67	75	0	77				1200		
Cuddapah	0	132	0	113	1	1	0.43	234	0	34	0	35	0	77	1	1	0	5	0	20	0	110	0	36	2	2	800			
East Godavari	0	423	0.59	169	2	2	1.8	222	0	44	0	15	0.5	200			0	12	0	19	0	63	0	24	7	7	1200			
Guntur	0	292	0	372			0.7	143	0	46	0	17	0	205	5	5	0	9	4.55	22	0	77	0	5	7	7	1200			
Krishna	0	312	0	96			0	177	0	44	1.39	72	0.56	355	2	2	0	8	0	36	0	86	0	1	6	0	4	1200		
Kurnool	0.97	207	0	120			0	224	0	63	0	25	0	160	7	7	0	10	0	33	0	109	0	233	5	0	1	1200		
Nellore	0	314	0.72	276			0.5	202	0	60	0	18	0	153	1	1	0	11	0	52	0	98	0	13			0	1	1200	
Prakasam	0.44	228	0	423			0	147	0	51	0	17	0	176	3	3	0	5	0	27	1.92	104	0	15	4	4	1200			
Srikakulam	0	181	0.33	303			0	74	0	29	0	4	0	160	1	1	0	1	0	2	0	41			2	2	800			
Visakhapatnam	0	400	0.86	232	3	3	0	70	0	66	0	41	0.17	589	11	11	0	23	1.2	83	0	45	0	22	13	0	1	1600		
Vizianagaram	0	124	0	157			0	172	0	52	0	31	0	385	3	3	5.26%	19	3.7	27	0	72	0.66	152	6	6	1200			
West Godavari	0.22	452	0.72	277			0.52	194	6.67	15	0	7	0	130			0	7	0	33	0	78	0	2	1	1	1200			

Table 28 : HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Migration status of Spouse

State/District	Yes		No		Not Applicable		Grand Total
	%	N	%	N	%	N	
Andhra Pradesh	0.39	257	0.30	15331	0	8	15600
Anantapur	0	45	0.45	1554	0	1	1600
Chittoor	0	52	0.61	1148			1200
Cuddapah	0	3	0.13	797			800
East Godavari	0	7	0.50	1193			1200
Guntur	0	17	0.17	1182			1200
Krishna	0	1	0.25	1195	0	4	1200
Kurnool	0	10	0.17	1189	0	1	1200
Nellore	0	26	0.26	1172	0	1	1200
Prakasam	0	73	0.27	1127			1200
Srikakulam	0	5	0.13	795			800
Visakhapatnam	0	2	0.25	1596	0	1	1600
Vizianagaram	8.33	12	0.17	1188			1200
West Godavari	0	4	0.42	1195			1200

Table 29 : HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees based on HIV tested history

State/District	YES		NO		G. Total
	%	N	%	N	
Andhra Pradesh	0.38	8741	0.20	6856	15600
Anantapur	0.39	764	0.48	836	1600
Chittoor	0.98	407	0.38	793	1200
Cuddapah	0.31	322	0	478	800
East Godavari	0.58	857	0.29	343	1200
Guntur	0.23	434	0.13	766	1200
Krishna	0.19	1052	0.68	148	1200
Kurnool	0.37	542	0	658	1200
Nellore	0.43	703	0	496	1200
Prakasam	0.38	782	0	418	1200
Srikakulam	0.32	315	0	485	800
Visakhapatnam	0.35	1153	0	446	1600
Vizianagaram	0.13	791	0.49	409	1200
West Godavari	0.48	619	0.34	580	1200

Table 30: District-wise HIV Prevalence trend 2002-2019

District	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2009	2011	2013	2015	2017	2019
Anantapur	1.25	1.00	1.50	1.38	1.38	1.00	0.88	0.63	0.19	0.25	0.44	0.44
Chittoor	1.00	0.75	1.63	1.60	0.38	0.63	1.63	0.50	0.54	0.17	0.33	0.58
Cuddapah		1.88	2.00	0.63	1.63	0.88	2.25	2.25	0.75	0.38	0.13	0.13
East Godavari	2.99	3.13	2.38	2.50	1.75	1.88	1.50	1.25	0.87	0.58	0.58	0.50
Guntur	4.00	3.25	2.50	2.75	1.75	1.84	2.50	1.08	0.83	0.42	0.17	0.17
Krishna	2.25	1.38	1.88	1.75	1.51	1.92	0.67	1.00	0.33	0.08	0.50	0.25
Kurnool	0.50	0.38	0.50	0.75	0.88	0.50	1.25	0.58	0.59	0.17	0.67	0.17
Nellore	1.00	1.50	2.50	1.13	1.75	1.50	1.00	0.33	0.50	0.25	0.67	0.25
Prakasam		2.75	2.88	2.88	2.63	1.33	1.08	0.25	1.34	0.51	0.17	0.25
Srikakulam		0.88	2.50	0.88	1.39	0.25	0.38	0.63	0.63	0.25	0.38	0.13
Visakhapatnam	0.75	1.63	1.13	1.50	0.38	0.38	0.58	0.63	0.63	0.44	0.27	0.25
Vizianagaram		1.13	1.13	1.63	0.88	0.63	0.88	0.33	0.33	0.17	0.42	0.25
West Godavari		2.26	2.38	3.14	2.41	1.84	2.08	0.77	0.50	0.45	0.08	0.42

5.2 HIV Prevalence trend at district level

CHAPTER 6

SUMMARY

The 16th round of HSS among pregnant women in 2019 was implemented at 39 sites across 13 districts in Andhra Pradesh collecting a total of 15600 complete data forms and biological specimens following consecutive sampling method and linked anonymous strategy as in previous round.

The median age of respondents were 22 years in the state and ranged between 15 and 46 years across the districts. The overall HIV prevalence among ANC clinic attendees in Andhra Pradesh in 2019 was low at 0.30%. District-wise, Chittoor (0.58 %), East Godavari (0.50%), Anantapur (0.44%) and West Godavari (0.42%), recorded higher HIV prevalence than that of the state average (0.30 %). Vizianagaram, Visakhapatnam, Prakasam, Nellore and Krishna recorded a prevalence of 0.25%, whereas it was 0.17% in Kurnool and Guntur and 0.13% in Srikakulam and Cuddapah.

HIV prevalence among ANC clinic attendees exhibits a declining trend at the state level as well as in most districts. A rising trend in recent past has been noted in Chittoor and West Godavari.

In general, HIV prevalence was higher among older group women and those at higher order pregnancies and urban residents. Higher the literacy status, lower was the prevalence. Prevalence was the highest among pregnant women who were non-agricultural labours. Pregnant women with migrant spouses or spouses working as trucker, hotel staffs, large business owners or local transport workers also have higher prevalence.

Findings from 2019 round of ANC HSS corroborates with previous rounds showing a low and declining trend at the state level, with persistent geographical diversity at district level. Sustained declining trend among ANC clients nationally and at the state-level, is positive indicator of the successful response of the National AIDS Control Programme (NACP). However, district-level fluctuating trends is a continuing challenge. The findings will be used as a compass by the policy makers and programme managers towards achieving 'End of AIDS' as a public health threat by 2030.

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